

The Challenge

Brand new devices:

- 80 types of Electrical and Electronic Equipment (EEE)
- 328 Different Manufacturer Brands
- 6 Models per Brand & EEE Type

Over 150,000 different devices

Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE):

- Devices aged 30 years to 1 month
- Damaged: broken, crushed, dirty
- Incomplete: missing essential components

Over 2 million different references

High heterogeneity

Bottlenecks and solutions

Difficulty to identify WEEE

Database of Brand-new devices

- Market Catalogues** → Manufacturer brand websites
- Market Analysis** → Market volume and forecast reports
- Legal Policies** → Ministry and legal institutions

Bottlenecks

- Lack of technical and manufacturing data
- Significant gap between market information and WEEE recycling practices

Content & Potential Use

Content:

- Images
- Product details: Brand, model
- Physical specifications: size, weight, Nd-PM components
- Nd-PM type (if available)

Benefits & Stakeholders

Benefits

- Identification of devices containing Nd-based PMs → REE recovery ↑
- Effortless sorting within WEEE piles → Efficiency ↑
- Easy integration with new Nd-PM identification systems → Employee ergonomics ↑
- Heterogeneity challenges ↓ Scalability ↑

- 9% database
14 brands
43 models
233,000 units sold
- 64% database
56 brands
303 models
251,000 units sold
- 6% database
6 brands
28 models
2.5 million units sold
- 12% database
13 brands
57 models
656.000 units sold
- 9% database
21 brands
45 models
253K units sold